

Liquid Crystals^ψ

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I greatly value the privilege of being invited this year to deliver this lecture, with which is associated the name of Acharya Jnan Chand Ghosh, a great eminent chemist, educationist, researcher and administrator. I am highly thankful to the authorities of the Indian Chemical Society for this honour.

The term 'Liquid Crystals' seems to be a self-contradiction, as it suggests that a substance is in two quite different states of matter at the same time. A crystal can not possess the properties of a perfect liquid or vice versa. Conventionally, matter exists in one of the three well-defined states of aggregation, namely, solids, liquids and gases, each having properties characteristic of its own. The transition from one state to another normally occurs at a very precise temperature. When pure crystalline solid is heated beyond its melting temperature, it undergoes a single transition to isotropic liquid. Ice-water is such a common phase transition. There are, however, many organic compounds that do not immediately transform to liquid phase when heated beyond the melting temperature but exhibit more than a single transition from solid to liquid showing the existence of one or more intermediate phases, exhibiting the properties of both solids and liquids. For example, *p*-azoxyanisole when heated does not transform into the liquid state but adopts a structure (turbid condition) that is both birefringent and fluid, the consistency varying with different compounds from that of a paste to that of a freely flowing liquid. The transitions are definite and precisely reversible. Materials undergoing such a phase transition are called liquid crystals.

Liquid crystals are known for about a hundred years. The credit for the discovery of 'liquid crystalline' phenomenon is given to an Austrian botanist Reinitzer¹. He observed that the compound cholesteryl benzoate appeared to have two melting points. At 145° the solid structure collapsed to form a turbid liquid (liquid crystal), which on further heating became transparent at 179°, giving a true isotropic liquid. In 1890, Lehmann² reported that ammonium oleate and *p*-azoxyphenetole exhibited the turbid state intermediate between truly crystalline and liquid states. Lehmann further showed that the cloudy turbid liquid showed degrees of molecular orderliness. Between crossed polarisers it was observed that though the turbid liquid would flow, it also exhibited optical anisotropy, characteristic of crystals. A birefringent fluid can also be formed when certain compounds are treated with a controlled amount of water or polar solvent. These birefringent systems are formed with certain rather large molecules. Lehmann described this state as fluid crystals and established for the first time the terminology 'liquid crystals'. Friedel³ suggested that this state should rather be called 'mesomorphic state' of matter because of its intermediate nature (Greek *mesos*, intermediate; *morphe*, form). Many other terms such as mesomorphic state, mesoform, mesophase, mesogen, anisotropic liquid, fluid crystals have been proposed and are used but the term 'liquid crystals' is still widely used.

Types of liquid crystals

Liquid crystals have been divided into two categories, thermotropic liquid crystals and

^ψAcharya J. C. Ghosh Memorial Lecture (1991) delivered under the auspices of the Indian Chemical Society on 16 July 1994 at Sardar Patel University, Vallabh Vidyanagar.

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lyotropic liquid crystals in accordance with the manner in which these are obtained.

Thermotropic liquid crystals :

Liquid crystals formed by heating solids are known as thermotropic liquid crystals.

Lyotropic liquid crystals :

The liquid crystalline system formed when certain compounds are treated with a controlled amount of water or the polar solvent is known as lyotropic liquid crystals. The properties of this birefringent fluids can resemble those of the birefringent fluids formed by heating solids.

Although the term lyotropic and thermotropic are widely used, Gray and Winsor⁴ prefer the terms amphiphilic (for lyotropic) and non-amphiphilic (for thermotropic).

With a large number of liquid crystalline substances available, Friedel carried out detailed optical studies of these compounds and classified them into three types as smectic, nematic and cholesteric. Smectic and nematic are the most common types of mesophases and the study of their optical properties made it possible to assign structures to them. These structures do not extend uniformly throughout the melt but the whole melt is composed of the random orientations of groups or swarms of molecules as proposed by Bose's swarm theory⁵. The word smectic is derived from the greek word meaning soaplike and has no specific significance. It was first used for ammonium oleate a soap-salt, it being the first smectic substance known. The mesophase is turbid and viscous forming greasy droplets. The word nematic is derived from the Greek word *nema* meaning threadlike and has a special meaning in that many nematic phases have a characteristic threaded appearance when examined in polarised light under the microscope. The mesophase is turbid and mobile milky liquid. The third type of phase, the cholesteric phase, a turbid and mobile phase, is so called because it is shown mainly by derivatives of cholesterol. It has certain characteristics of its own which are markedly different from smectic and nematic mesophases. Number of compounds are known to show one or the other of these mesophases. Some examples are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Compd	Melting point (°C)	Transition point (°C)
Smectic		
Ethyl <i>p</i> -azoxybenzoate	114.0	122.5
Ethyl <i>p</i> -azoxycinnamate	140.0	249.0
Nematic		
<i>p</i> -Azoxyanisole	118.0	136.0
<i>p</i> -Azoxyphenetole	137.0	168.0
Cholesteric		
Cholesteryl benzoate	149.0	187.0
Cholesteryl cinnamate	160.0	215.0

Many mesomorphic substances which have been studied are either of exclusively smectic structure or of exclusively nematic structure, but some can exist as both types of structures, smectic followed by nematic, and in these cases there are always definite transition temperatures defining the stability of different phases, which are completely reproducible. A few substances have been found to possess more than one smectic phase and here also the temperature range of stability of the different phases are sharply defined. This is known as polymesomorphism.

n-Octoxybenzal-*p*-propylaniline exhibits four liquid crystalline modifications⁶. Although there are many examples of polymesomorphism of smectic mesophase, there are no authenticated examples of polymesomorphism of nematic mesophase.

Mesomorphic transitions so far discussed occur on heating the substances and these transitions reverse in the opposite direction on cooling. Such a mesophase is called the enantiotropic mesophase. Quite frequently, however, the crystalline solid melts normally to give an isotropic liquid at temperature T_1 , but when the isotropic liquid is cooled, supercooling may occur and mesophase appears below the melting point at temperature T_2 , and before crystallisation occurs. Such a mesophase is given the name monotropic mesophase. The sequence of changes of state for a compound exhibiting monotropic mesophase may be represented as

Such a monotropic mesophase is observed on cooling; this monotropic temperature is also reversible, and on raising the temperature before crystallisation, the isotropic liquid is obtained at T_2 itself.

The literature on the mesomorphic state has much confusion in the terminology used for designating the temperatures at which the transitions take place. Some authors refer to the mesomorphic-isotropic transition as the melting point or clearing point whereas others refer to the collapse of the crystal lattice to mesomorphic state as the melting point or transition point. Here we shall refer the transition from solid to mesomorphic or isotropic liquid as melting point. The other transitions will be referred to as smectic-smectic, smectic-nematic, cholesteric-isotropic transition temperatures. Recently, terminology has been adopted for the phase transitions, C-M (crystal-mesophase), S_1 - S_2 (smectic₁-smectic₂), S-N (smectic-nematic), N-I (nematic-isotropic), Ch-I (cholesteric-isotropic) points etc.

Many organic materials exhibit more than a single transition in passing from solid to liquid, thereby necessitating the existence of one or more intermediate phases. It is not surprising that the molecular ordering in these intermediate phases, known as 'mesophases', lies between that of a solid and that of an isotropic liquid. The partial ordering of the molecules in a given mesophase may be either translational or rotational or both. Clearly, translational order can be realised regardless of molecular shape, whereas rotational order has meaning only when the constituent molecules are non-spherical (elongated). Thus molecular structure is an important factor in determining the kind and extent of ordering in a particular mesophase.

Two basically different types of mesophases have been identified. First, there are those that retain a 3-dimensional crystal lattice, but are char-

acterised by substantial rotational disorder (i.e. disordered crystal mesophases), and second, there are those with no lattice, which are therefore fluid, but nevertheless exhibit considerable rotational order (i.e. ordered fluid mesophases). Molecular structure is in fact important and molecules comprising one of these two types of mesophases are distinctly different in shape from molecules comprising the other. Indeed, with the possible exception of some polymorphous smectic materials, there are no known substances that show both disordered crystal and ordered fluid mesophases. Disordered crystal mesophases are known as 'plastic crystals'. In most cases plastic crystals are composed of 'globular' (i.e. essentially spherical) molecules. These are liquid-like solids. Ordered fluid mesophases are commonly called 'liquid crystals' and are most often composed of elongated molecules. In these mesophases, the molecules show some degree of rotational order (and in some cases partial translational order as well) even though the crystal lattice has been destroyed. Lack of lattice requires that these mesophases be fluid and are ordered fluid phases. It is this simultaneous possession of liquid-like (fluidity) and solid-like (molecular order) character in a single phase that makes liquid crystals unique and gives rise to so many interesting properties. These are solid-like liquids. These mesophases do not satisfy all the criteria of either a true solid or a true liquid but in fact exhibit many physical properties that are characteristic of both; for example, liquid crystals flow but their optical properties such as birefringence are those normally expected of regular solids. Molecules within plastic crystals have rotational and diffusional mobilities approaching that of the liquid phase although the solid condition is maintained. In liquid crystals, molecules are free to move but their rotational mobility is restricted; in plastic crystals, molecules are free to rotate in place and to some extent change lattice sites, but they still form a regular crystalline superstructure.

Phenomenon of mesomorphism is essentially a consequence of molecular shape. A general condition for the formation of a mesophase is that the molecules comprising the system be either

(a) elongated and in some cases also flat (possibility of liquid crystallinity) or (b) approximately spherical (possibility of plastic crystallinity). A rough determining factor for mesomorphism is, therefore, the length-to-breadth ratio of the molecular frame, which may be denoted by R ; where $R \geq 1$, there is possibility of liquid crystal formation and if $R \approx 1$, a plastic crystal may occur.

essentially intact. Smectic liquid crystals retain a good deal of two-dimensional order. The layered nature of this liquid crystal structure was suggested from the fact that smectogenic solids when melted on a very clean glass slide produce a terraced texture. The strata of many molecular lengths are called Grandjean planes. In the smectic phase the layers of molecules are quite flexible.

Smectic liquid crystals

Smectic mesophase has a stratified structure; the long molecules are arranged side by side, parallel to one another and in series of layers, with their long axes approximately normal to the plane of layers. Though the smectic phase is a highly ordered phase, the spacing of the molecules within each layer is, however, not uniform as it would be in a true crystal. The fluidity of the phase is attributed to the fact that the layers can glide over one another in hundreds like individual units in pack of cards (Fig. 1).

The stratified structure of the smectic phase was inferred from the formation of stepped drops observed under the microscope and confirmed by X-ray analysis. Smectic liquid crystals arise from organic solids that themselves are stratified. The melting process evidently disrupts the end-to-end molecular cohesions, but the temperature at which the mesophase is stable is not sufficient to break apart lateral associations and the layers remain

When a smectic phase is formed on cooling the isotropic liquid, it first appears frequently in the form of non-spherical characteristic elongated birefringent particles which are known as batonnets. These coalesce and show evidence of a focal conic structure. The focal conic structure was an important means of detecting the smectic mesophase. It extends all over the specimen and when examined under polarised light it gives a fan-like appearance. When observed under the microscope the smectic phase appears to be quite immobile unlike the nematic phase. Whatever be the structure, the smectic mesophase is a positive uniaxial crystal. It is unaffected by magnetic and electric fields.

From the structural point of view, the smectic liquid crystals have layered structures with a well-defined interlayer spacing, which can be measured by X-ray diffraction. Smectics are thus more ordered than nematics. A number of different classes of smectic liquid crystals are known which differ from each other in the way of layer formation. As many as nine such classes of smectic liquid

crystals are tentatively known. However, except for the three that have been well characterised, considerable uncertainty still exists about the exact nature of the molecular ordering in these phases. The best understood smectic phases are smectic A, B and C phases. In smectic A, the molecules are upright in each layer with their centres irregularly spaced in a liquid like fashion. The thickness of each layer is of the order of the length of free molecules. The lateral forces between the molecules are strong as compared with interlayer attraction. As a consequence, the layers are able to slide over one another relatively easily. Thus this phase has fluid properties, though it is usually much more viscous than nematic liquid crystal. The system is optically uniaxial. In smectic B, the molecular centres in each layer are hexagonal closepacked. Smectic C is a tilted form of smectic A, i.e. the molecules are inclined with respect to the layers. This phase is optically biaxial. Smectic D has been reported to be cubic and is an exception to the rule, that the smectics have well defined layered structures. A few more distinct modifications are reported but their structures are not known with any certainty. The smectic B phase is the most ordered of the three major smectics A, B and C. If a material is able to display all three phases, the sequence with increasing temperature is always $\text{Solid} \rightleftharpoons \text{B} \rightleftharpoons \text{C} \rightleftharpoons \text{A}$. For a material having nematic and smectic trimorphous phases, the sequence of mesophase stability with increasing temperature will be $\text{S} \rightleftharpoons \text{B} \rightleftharpoons \text{C} \rightleftharpoons \text{A} \rightleftharpoons \text{N} \rightleftharpoons \text{Isotropic liquid}$.

A subdivision of smectic phase into two groups as with structured layers and unstructured layers is proposed by Saupe⁷. The textures of these smectics have been identified by miscibility studies. Much work on classification of smectics has been done by Sackmann and Demus⁸ in accordance with the textures observed in the mesophases. The textures observed are

Smectic-A :	Simple fan-shaped texture Simple polygon texture
Smectic-C :	Broken fan-shaped textut Broken polygon texture
Smectic-B :	Fan-shaped texture Polygon texture Mosaic texture

Nematic liquid crystals

The nematic phase is not as highly ordered as the smectic mesophase. In the nematic phase the molecules are arranged parallel or nearly parallel to each other but it displays no layer flow. The molecules are able to move past each other in the direction of their longitudinal axes but they are not separated into layers. The molecular arrangement may be likened to a long box filled with round pencils which can roll around and slide back and forth but remain parallel to one another in the direction of long axes (Fig. 1). The nematic phase is more similar to a true liquid state. Like true liquids, nematic liquids give only diffusion haloes with X-rays indicating that there is no layer structure of the smectic phase. Nematic substances in general are more fluid than the smectic ones. The nematic mesoforms are oriented by electric and magnetic fields. In an electric field the nematic molecules set themselves with their axes at right angles to the lines of force and in the magnetic field they lie with their long axes parallel to the lines of force. There being no stratified structure, nematic pahses exhibit neither focal conic structure or grandjean planes and in contrast to the formation of batonnets in a smectic phase, the nematic substances separate as spherical drops from the melt or solution, which coalesce to give the threaded structure.

Attempts have been made to explain the phenomenon of mesomorphism. No theory has been established which answers the question successfully. The majority of mesomorphic compounds are comprised of long, rod-shaped or lath-shaped molecules, frequently carrying dipolar groups situated either centrally or terminally. Because of the elongated molecular shape and rotational movements existing between neighbouring dipolar molecules, there will be a tendency for the molecules to arrange themselves parallel to one another. These molecules on the basis of Bose's swarm theory⁵ are not oriented in the same direction throughout the whole medium, but are grouped in aggregates or swarms. Molecules within each swarm lie parallel or approximately so, but in a direction that is random to the molecules of

other swarm in the medium. From this point of view, the liquid crystal structure resembles a mass of 'small crystals' but without the properties of a single crystal, because of the mobility of the molecules which can move in and out of an aggregate to become a part of the medium or to enter a neighbouring aggregate. The aggregates are not rigid and are subject to mechanical deformations. The swarm hypothesis explains the turbid appearance of the liquid crystalline state. It explains the effect of applied electric and magnetic fields and can account for the double refraction of liquid crystalline materials.

Swarm hypothesis has many limitations. The true structure of this state of matter will be found to be more nearly continuous. Zocher⁹ proposed the distortion hypothesis which is based on the concept of continuum for the mesophase such that the orientation of the molecules changes in a continuous fashion throughout the bulk of the mesophase, now referred to as the continuum theory of liquid crystals. This hypothesis has also its limitations.

Smectic structure is not interpreted in terms of either the swarm theory or the distortion hypothesis. Evidently no hypothesis or theory has been proposed to explain the smectic structure.

Cholesteric liquid crystals

As the name indicates cholesteric liquid crystals can be observed in the cholesterol derivatives especially esters, though cholesterol itself does not form liquid crystals. In addition to cholesterol, other sterol derivatives also exhibit mesomorphism. In cholesteric substances, molecules are arranged in layers. The layers are parallel similar to the nematic phase. While the individual molecules in cholesteric phase are essentially flat, the side-chain of methyl groups projects upwards from the plane of each molecule, some hydrogen atoms extend below. The direction of the long axes

of the molecules in a chosen layer is slightly displaced from the corresponding direction in adjacent layers. The overall displacement traces a helical path as illustrated in Fig. 2. Liquid crystals

Fig. 2

of this type are by far the most optically active. In many ways the properties of cholesteric phase resemble those of the smectic and nematic phases. The cholesteryl esters do not necessarily form only cholesteric type liquid crystals. Some exhibit both smectic and cholesteric behaviour. The higher cholesteryl esters show only smectic behaviour and the lower ones only cholesteric behaviour; but the intermediate ones exhibit both types. Apparently there have not been any examples found of compounds which exhibit both cholesteric and nematic phases, whereas each commonly occurs, in association with the smectic phase. According to Friedel, cholesteric phase is considered a special case of nematic phase. When isotropic melt of cholesteric material is cooled a confocal texture of the cholesteric structure is obtained.

Mixtures of dextro- and leavorotatory cholesteric substances give the nematic phase. Similarly, nematic liquid crystals can be transformed into cholesteric liquid crystal by dissolving an optically active compound in it. The amount of light diffused by nematic mesophase is similar to that diffused by cholesteric mesophase. The study of the properties of the cholesteric mesophase in detail has proved beyond doubt that cholesteric mesophase is nematic in type. Cholesteric mesophase has a fluidity like the nematic phase. It can be oriented by the electric and magnetic fields like the nematic mesophase. Cholesteric mesophase has certain char-

Fig 1

acteristics of its own which are markedly different from smectic and nematic mesophases. When illuminated by white light, the most striking property of the cholesteric mesophase is that of scattering the light to give vivid colours. It is optically negative, while smectic and nematic structures are positive. The structure shows strong rotatory power.

Cholesteric liquid crystals can occur as (i) focal conic texture, (ii) planar or plane texture, (iii) blue phase or isotropic texture.

Mesomorphism formed by amphiphilic compounds (lyotropic mesomorphism)

The amphiphilic mesogens frequently form mesophases either at room temperature or at higher temperature, which can incorporate into their structure considerable amounts of water and/or organic compounds. On account of the marked effect of solvents, in particular, water, the amphiphilic mesophases have frequently been termed lyotropic mesophase. Amphiphilic compounds are characterised by possessing two groups in the same molecule which differ in their solubility relationship. These are (a) a hydrophilic group which tends to be water soluble and hydrocarbon insoluble and (b) a lipophilic group which tends to be hydrocarbon soluble and water insoluble. Typical hydrophilic groups are $-\text{OH}$, $-\text{CO}_2\text{H}$, $-\text{CO}_2\text{Na}$, $-\text{SO}_3\text{K}$, $-\text{PO}_4-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{NH}_3^+$, $-\text{NMe}_3\text{Br}$ etc., and typical lipophilic groups are $-\text{C}_n\text{H}_{2n+1}$, $\text{C}_n\text{H}_{2n+1}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$ etc.

Lyotropic substances are always strongly birefringent, their physical nature varying from a turbid free flowing fluid to a waxy solid. The first lyotropic substance ammonium oleate reported by Lehmann, which gradually breaks down in presence of water (solvent) may be represented as

Substances like soap, soap-like alkali salts of naphthoic acids, resin acids, substituted phenanthrene sulphonic acids etc, show mesomorphic state under controlled action of water. Alcoholic solutions of

these compounds do not generally show anisotropic behaviour; so a high degree of hydration appears to be a necessary prerequisite for the occurrence of many lyotropic mesophases.

McBain¹⁰ has discussed forms of mesomorphism in soap solutions. Lyotropic liquid crystalline states analogous to the smectic and nematic thermotropic liquid crystals have been clearly demonstrated; but they are not so simple as in the case of thermotropic mesophases. Amphiphilic mesophase is formed by the ordered arrangements of various types of micelles or aggregates of amphiphilic molecules. Mesophase in binary systems of amphiphiles and water may be classified as (a) the neat phase (G phase), (b) the middle phase (M_1 phase), (c) the viscous isotropic phase (V_1 phase) and (d) the inverse phase (V_2 and M_2 phases).

Chemical constitution and mesomorphic state

There is a close relationship between the molecular structure and the mesomorphism of a compound. However, a characteristic structure of a molecule that will show the mesomorphic state cannot be easily defined. Organic compounds are the ones known to exhibit the liquid crystalline state. Mesomorphism is found in aromatic, aliphatic and multiring compounds. An example of a simple aliphatic compound showing liquid crystallinity is 2,4-nonadienoic acid while the simplest aromatic compounds are *p*-propoxybenzoic acid, *p*-butylbenzoic acid, *p*-azoxyanisole, *p*-methoxycinnamic acid etc.

The existence of mesomorphic states may be explained by considering the molecular structure of compounds showing liquid crystalline behaviour. The molecules of all such compounds possess a striking common feature in having a great length relative to the other dimensions. Cholesteryl molecules are considerably broad but here length predominates over breadth and thickness. In general, the molecules of a liquid crystalline compound are elongated, rod or lath-shaped, thin and often flat, possessing middle and terminal polar groups. The shape of the molecules favours a parallel alignment of molecules to one another like a bundle of pencils leading to the closest possible packing in the crystalline or liquid crys-

talline state. However, rod-shaped molecules do not invariably form liquid crystals. Molecular branching tends to inhibit the formation of liquid crystals. Molecules which form liquid crystals have dipole in their structure – often a strong dipole towards the centre of the molecule and a weak dipole towards the end of the molecules.

In the solid state, the long, thin, flat molecules of this type of compounds pack together in layers in an orderly manner; on raising the temperature, it is possible for the layers of the molecules to slide over each other whilst still preserving within each layer much of the original order. This can be likened to a number of brushes piled one upon another, able to move sideways while keeping the molecules (bristles) in parallel arrangement. This produces a smectic mesophase and compounds with terminal attractions which are relatively easily broken but possess fairly strong lateral attractions between the molecules are of this type. In some cases lateral attraction is less strong (or may be weakened as the temperature rises) permitting the molecules to slide past each other in the direction of their long axes. This produces a nematic mesophase in which 'swarms' of molecules aligned in parallel can persist. When the temperature is sufficiently high, order is destroyed and the random arrangement of molecules produces isotropic liquid. This is illustrated in Fig. 1.

The attractions between the molecules arise from the presence of suitable polar groups. In addition, the compounds need to be sufficiently polarisable for dipole and induced dipole attraction to be significant and this is often achieved by the presence of benzene rings and multiple bonds. For compounds containing benzene rings, the substituents must occupy *para*-positions and be of such a kind that they link up at least one other benzene ring which also carries *para*-substituent. It is preferable that the linking group between the two benzene nuclei should be of a rigid nature. This can be represented as follows :

where X and Y are the terminal substituents and A the central linkage. The usual central linkages are $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-$, $-(\text{CH}=\text{CH})_n-$, $-\text{C}\equiv\text{C}-$, $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$, $-\text{N}=\text{N}-$, $-\text{CH}=\text{CH}-\text{C}(=\text{O})-\text{O}-$, $-\text{CH}=\text{N}-$, $-\text{C}(=\text{O})-\text{O}-$, $-\text{CH}=\text{N}-\text{N}=\text{CH}-$, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-$, $(-\text{CO}_2\text{H})_2$, $-\text{O}-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}_2-\text{O}-$, $-\text{CH}=\text{N}-$ etc. When more than two benzene rings are linked through more than one central group, the liquid crystalline properties are enhanced the most.

The linkage of benzene rings through the *ortho*- or *meta*-position is not favourable to the liquid crystal formation because the molecules then become non-linear. However, linearity and rigidity are increased by linking up the benzene rings directly and thus biphenyls provide a rich source of liquid crystals which are thermally more stable than those of benzene substituted analogues. It is observed that the benzene ring plays an important role in the formation of liquid crystals. With the increase in the number of aromatic rings, the stability and phase length of the mesophases are increased.

For example,

with three benzene rings is an enantiotropic liquid crystal with a phase length of 140° from 142° to 282°. With an increase of one more benzene ring, the ester

containing four aromatic rings the region of stability is increased from 187° to red heat at which the substance decomposes; here the phase length is about 300°.

Despite its very high melting point (401°) and absence of terminal substituents the hydrocarbon *p*-pentaphenyl is a liquid crystal. (C 401 N 445 l).

Further, it is interesting to note that many liquid crystalline substances evaporate or distil before they change to isotropic liquid. The compound dianisalbenzidine

containing four benzene rings distils directly from the mesophase and the isotropic melt cannot be reached.

However, many compounds, molecular structure of which should give rise to liquid crystals do not, in fact, do so. Although the criteria of linearity is accepted as a favourable condition, other conditions should also obtain for the existence of liquid crystalline state; these are that the melting point of the compound should not be too high to cause thermal agitation sufficient to bring about disorder in the melt and that the intermolecular forces should be strong enough so that some order may be preserved in the melt when the crystal lattice breaks down. As strong intermolecular forces bring about high melting point, these two conditions are in opposition to one another and therefore, all compounds with long molecules do not form liquid crystals.

p-*n*-Propoxybenzoic acid has the simplest molecular structure to form liquid crystals. As such the length of the simple acid molecule is not enough to exhibit mesomorphism but the length of the acid molecule is increased by the hydrogen bond formation and mesomorphism arises from the association of acids forming a dimer through carboxylic groups, acquiring a linear structure similar in shape and size to the typical nematic substance *p*-azoxyanisole. The corresponding methyl ester of *p*-*n*-propoxybenzoic acid does not yield a mesomorph although it has a low melting point. *p*-Methoxy- and *p*-ethoxybenzoic acids, however, do not form liquid crystals which is attributed to their high melting points but the mixture of the two acids when melted yields nematic liquid crystal due to the lowering of their melting points. This provides an evidence in support of the statement that high melting points will cause thermal agitation resulting in the spontaneous disorder in the melt.

Effect of terminal substituents on liquid crystalline behaviour :

Replacement of terminal hydrogen in a molecule by another substituent enhances the potential of the system to form liquid crystals. If the unsubstituted compound forms liquid crystals, then the substituted compound will form liquid crystals which are in the majority of cases more thermally stable; only for smectic liquid crystals certain terminal substituents do reduce thermal stability. Terminal substituents usually raise the melting points, but they increase the liquid crystal thermal stability also.

Gray¹¹ studied the influence of terminal substituents in pure mesogenic compounds and obtained group efficiency orders in nematic and smectic systems. Dave and Vora¹² obtained group efficiency orders for the different substituents in cholesteric systems.

Effect of lateral substituents on liquid crystalline behaviour :

The side substituent may force apart the molecules and thus may reduce the intermolecular lateral cohesions but at the same time the side substituent may increase the molecular polarisability which in turn may increase the intermolecular attractions. However, if the substituents occupy certain pockets in the molecule so that the breadth effect is not manifest, it is found to increase the thermal stabilities.

Effect of molecular breadth on mesomorphism is interesting. Gray and Jones¹³ found that 6-*n*-alkoxy-2-naphthoic acids are mesomorphic, whereas 4-*n*-alkoxy-1-naphthoic acids are non-mesomorphic. Dave *et al.*¹⁴ reported that Schiff base compounds comprising naphthalene nuclei are mesomorphic but thermally less stable than the corresponding benzylidene Schiff base compounds. According to Gray¹⁵ the mesomorphic compound should have high length-to-breadth ratio and the molecule should contain groups which are permanently dipolar or readily polarisable. In the naphthalene compounds if length can be increased to balance the length-to-breadth ratio, the molecule will exhibit mesomorphism. Liquid crystalline compounds containing phenanthrene, fluorene and fluorenone are also known

Mesomorphism in homologous series :

With a view to correlate the effect of structural modifications, attempts have been made to study the mesomorphic properties of different homologous series of organic compounds. It is observed that when the alkyl chains are short, the systems are either non-mesomorphic or nematic; as the chain length increases, smectic properties begin to appear and as the smectic phase increases the nematic phase decreases with the successive chain increment, till in the higher homologues, only smectic phase is found. Generally, when the mesomorphic transition temperatures are plotted against the number of carbon atoms in the alkyl chain, the transition points lie on two smooth curves, the upper curve corresponding to the compounds with an even number of carbon atoms in the alkyl chain and the lower one to those with an odd number of carbon atoms in the alkyl chain. For a system with *n*-alkyl group attached direct to the ring the reverse situation arises because the oxygen of the ether link in the alkoxy group is equivalent stereochemically to a methylene unit.

The odd-even effect becomes less marked as the series is ascended and the two curves merge later in the series. The smectic-nematic temperatures usually do not alternate and lie on a smooth curve which rises steeply at first, then levels out and merges with the falling nematic-isotropic curve. However, there are cases in which the smectic-nematic transition curve does not merge with the falling nematic-isotropic curve and the last members of the series exhibit nematic mesophase alongwith the smectic mesophase. There are also cases in which smectic-nematic and smectic-cholesteric temperatures alternate. In the case of cholesteryl fatty acid ester series, the smectic-cholesteric transition point curve does not merge with the falling cholesteric-isotropic curve and the cholesteric mesophase persists upto the last member of the series.

Re-entrant nematic phase

A nematogenic mesophase with a sequence solid-nematic-smectic-isotropic on cooling will give reverse order sequence isotropic-smectic-nematic-solid. But certain mesogenic cyano compounds on

cooling exhibit an interesting sequence isotropic-nematic-smectic-nematic. The second nematic phase which occurs at a lower temperature than the smectic phase is called the 're-entrant nematic' phase. All these compounds have a highly polar cyano group attached to one end of the molecule, which results in strong anti-parallel correlations between neighbouring molecules. This in turn leads to a bilayer structure with interdigitated molecules in each bilayer. As the temperature and pressure are varied the molecular packing is altered slightly, and the resulting mobile change in the bilayer structure, appears to be responsible for the occurrence of the re-entrant nematic phase. The re-entrant nematic phase has a typical schlieren texture¹⁶.

trans-p-*n*-decyloxy- α -methyl-*p*'-cyanophenyl cinnamate

Disc-like mesogens

The distinctive feature of thermotropic liquid crystals formed by pure compounds is the rod-like or lath-like shape of the molecules. Simple plate-like or disc-like molecules, viz. pure benzene-hexan-alkanoates show thermotropic mesomorphism. The mesophases are very viscous and birefringent. The mesophase has a typical fan-shaped texture resembling the texture of some of the smectic phases and indicate highly ordered stratified structure. Based on X-ray data, a structure is proposed in which the discs are stacked one on top of the other in columns that constitute a hexagonal arrangement but the spacing between the discs in each column is irregular. The mesophase is a highly ordered lamellar type of liquid crystal¹⁷ (Fig. 3).

Plastic crystals (cubic mesophase)

In contrast to liquid crystals, which are solid-like liquids, plastic crystals, are liquid-like solids. Plastic crystal molecules are approximately spherical (globular) in shape and therefore, molecules that make this intermediate phase (notable examples are camphor, adamantane), are able to attain a large degree of rotational freedom before passing

R = n-C₄H₉ to n-C₉H₉
Benzene-hexa-n-alkanoate

Schematic representation of the structure of the mesophase. The discs are irregularly spaced to form liquid like columns

Fig 3

into a true liquid state. A definite crystal structure is maintained although it appears that intersite diffusion occurs rather readily. As a result of this high microscopic mobility these solids are quite readily deformed. It is this softness or plasticity that gives the mesophases their name. They can easily be extruded at relatively low pressure, and some have even consistency of butter. Perfluorocyclohexane flows under its own weight. They can easily be cut with a knife. Plastic crystals are thus neither true liquids wholly devoid of long range molecular order nor true crystalline solids, with molecules in regular long range orientational and positional order but constitute a further mesophase equivalent in status to Friedel's smectic and nematic mesophases.

Liquid crystals are typically formed by relatively elongated and rather rigid lath-like molecules which have restricted rotational freedom. Plastic crystals on the other hand are typically constituted by rather compact globular molecules, which when undergoing rotatory displacement acquire close-to-spherical symmetry. Formation of plastic crystals

is due to the capacity of the constituent molecules over a particular temperature range to arrange themselves in a cubic array while at the same time undergoing thermal rotatory displacement so that there is no long range orientational order between the molecules. Plastic crystals are among the most molecularly disordered of all mesophases and from this point of view, the most 'liquid' in character¹⁸.

Liquid crystal polymers

These are polymers containing liquid crystalline monomers. These monomeric units influence the alignment of molecules in the polymer and impart special properties to the polymer. Polymeric liquid crystals find a number of applications.

Liquid crystals in biological systems

Liquid crystals play an important role in nature. Most of the protein and fatty substances of animal bodies exist in the liquid crystalline state. This state seems to be especially suited to biological functions and may probably be the basis of vital

activity. Many living tissues like muscles, nerves, tendons and bones show the optical properties of double refraction; the degree of double refraction in some fibrous systems increases on stretching and decreases on contraction. Living sperms, composed in part of proteins, nucleoproteins and albumins have been shown to possess mesomorphic state. Aqueous solutions of certain viruses, e.g. tobacco mosaic virus exhibits lyotropic mesophase. The essential components of membrane of living cells and connective tissues show the significance of liquid crystals in them. There are several good theoretical reasons why matter in liquid crystalline state should play a part in the structure of living tissues. The preparation of artificial mesophase by ternary system of cholesterol, amphiphile (lecithin or polyoxyethylene ester) and solvent (water) has been mentioned. It is known that hemoglobin is liquid crystalline in nature.

Applications of liquid crystals

Liquid crystals have many odd and interesting optical and physical properties which can be exploited for practical advantages.

Cholesteric liquid crystals :

The important contributing factor in the application of cholesteric liquid crystals is its optical property. Perhaps the most widely exploited optical property of the cholesteric liquid crystal is the colour sensitivity. Most cholesteric substances are colourless as liquid crystals; however, they pass through series of bright colours when they are cooled through their liquid crystalline phase. At a given temperature the cholesteric material or combination of materials will always exhibit the same colour. The rate of change from colour to colour as well as the exact temperature at which the specific colour changes occur are invariable. Mixtures of cholesterics have found application in measurement of surface temperatures as well as detection of surface temperature variations (from -20° to $+250^{\circ}$). This property forms the basis for non-destructive testing of metal coatings, semi-conductor devices, printed circuit assemblies and related items in which flaws produce differential heat flow. Cholesteric liquid crystal mixtures have also been suggested for measuring

body skin temperature, to outline tumours etc. Any inflammation or constriction of the vessels will naturally affect the temperature of the skin; this will help in the location of inflammation, since the warmer areas will be outlined by the colour pattern. In gynecology, where there is a possibility that a caesarian section may be necessary, liquid crystals can be used to locate the placenta, thus avoiding the need for an X-ray. Disposable thermometers can be made using cholesteric liquid crystals encapsulated in foils. In psychology, cholesteric liquid crystals could be used as lie-detectors. The sensitivity of cholesteric liquid crystals to react to pressure as well as temperature by colour changes is used to make some very interesting publicity materials and toys. Cholesteric liquid crystals can be used as an analytical tool to detect the presence of very small amounts of gases or vapours by colour changes to the extent of about 1 ppm.

Nematic liquid crystals :

Nematic and nematic-cholesteric mixtures of substances have been used which have stimulated progress in electronic research and industry. Nematic liquid crystals possess the ability to scatter light depending on the strength of the applied electric field. A large number of liquid crystal devices (LCDs) are produced. A liquid crystal device differs fundamentally from an electronic display device such as a cathode ray tube, in that the liquid crystal device generates no light of its own but it scatters light. An LCD offers two advantages over other display devices : (a) it reflects light instead of generating it; thus it can be viewed under a wide range of light conditions including direct sunlight or a flood light, and (b) the liquid crystal device does not emit light and therefore draws much less power than light emitting diodes and is less expensive. Application of electric field to nematic liquid crystals involves a process of orientation of rod-like molecules in some direction with respect to that of the field.

A liquid crystal device (cell) is made by sandwiching a room temperature liquid crystal material between two glass plates which are coated

by some electrically conducting material such as tin oxide, the glass plates being kept apart preferably less than 150 microns. By applying the electric current (10–300 V) to the plates the liquid crystalline molecules can be oriented in the desired manner. The previously transparent cell thus can be made cloudy so that only diffused light passes through just as if it were a piece of frosted glass. The degree of cloudiness can be adjusted by varying the voltage. When the field is switched off the cell generally becomes transparent again within a few thousandth of a second. Such display systems can be used in certain types of light modulating devices, such as light valves, memory circuits, rear projection screens and display panels. This suggests new possibilities for flat TV screens, oscilloscopes, electro-optical indicating systems, outdoor electronic advertising and windows with variable transparency such as anti-dazzle wind screens. Liquid crystal display devices consisting of digital readouts are used in watches, calculators and several other instruments. Some liquid crystal substances could be useful in the computer industry, for making new computer elements with high memory capacity.

Nematic and smectic compounds are also used with success as stationary phases to separate compounds closely related and difficult to separate by general methods, e.g. gas liquid partition chromatography; they are extremely valuable as they act selectively as solvents in separations. Another interesting use of nematic structure is as a solvent in nuclear magnetic resonance studies to obtain special information, difficult to obtain by other techniques.

Mixed liquid crystals (mixed mesomorphism)

Just as the melting points of the solids are depressed by the addition of other substances, so also are the transition temperatures of liquid crystals lowered by the addition of foreign substances. When a mesomorphic compound is mixed with another mesomorphic or non-mesomorphic component, the solid-mesomorphic and mesomorphic-isotropic transition points may be depressed and the degree of depression will depend upon the concentration of the added component in the

mixture. If both the components of a range of binary mixtures are enantiotropic mesogens, the mixtures will give enantiotropic mesophases. Binary mixtures of a mesogen with other non-mesomorphic compounds, exhibit mesophases which may be enantiotropic or monotropic. Liquid crystallinity in binary mixtures of non-mesogenic compounds is also known. The phenomenon of mixed liquid crystals may be called mixed mesomorphism.

Few systematic studies have been made on the binary systems of substances that exhibit mesomorphic state. In early 1950s Dave and Dewar¹⁹ examined the problem by studying the behaviour of mixtures of varying composition, each mixture containing one component which is capable of giving a nematic mesophase (*p*-azoxyanisole) and the other which gives no anisotropic phase. They concluded that the liquid phase produced by heating the mixture of solids is a homogeneous single phase, whether it be mesomorphic or not. There was no indication that two distinct liquid phases, one isotropic and another anisotropic can coexist over a range of temperature for a binary mixture of given composition. Genuine mixed liquid crystals are formed. Using a variety of 'solute' molecules in *p*-azoxyanisole, it was found that the main qualitative difference in the phase diagrams lies in the slopes of the anisotropic liquid-isotropic liquid transition lines. The slopes are steeper the more the 'solute' molecules depart from the phenomenon of mesomorphism. Dave and Dewar extended their studies to the effect of structure on the transition temperature of mixed liquid crystals. It seems reasonable that any substance with anisotropic molecules would form a liquid crystal if it could be obtained in liquid form at a sufficiently low temperature. Where only one component appears to exhibit mesomorphism, the other must have a potential or a latent mesomorphic property. These substances that do not exhibit mesomorphism but potentially possess it evade observation because transition to the liquid lies below the normal melting point. Such latent transitions can be obtained by extrapolation. If the molecules of the two components differ in shape and size there will be difficulty in packing them together. The transition lines in the phase diagrams should then be concave upwards (*p*-azoxyanisole : anisic acid).

Dave and Dewar reached several interesting conclusions from their study of binary systems of a nematogen (*p*-azoxyanisole) with a second component a non-mesogen, similar in shape and size (e.g. azo, azoxy, Schiff base compounds). The transition lines are almost linear. Lower the slope, the greater the tendency for the second component to form a mesomorphic system with *p*-azoxyanisole; the slope of the transition line should provide an indication of the virtual transition temperature of the second non-mesogenic component. Slopes are similar for isomeric pair of Schiff bases (MeO, Cl). Presence of two polar groups is necessary for a low value of the slope of transition line. The effect of the terminal groups are approximately additive irrespective of sign; 'Group slope' values for the terminal groups can be ascribed such that the slope of the transition line for a given compound could be expressed as the sum of the group slopes for the terminal substituents present. A group efficiency order in promoting nematic behaviour could be deduced. Such an extended group efficiency order based on the results of Dave *et al.*¹⁹⁻²¹ is given below :

NO₂ > OEt > OMe > OCO.Et > OPr > OCO Me > NMe₂ > Me = Cl
0.5 1.0 2.0 2.4 2.5 3.0 5.6 7.2 7.2

F = Br > I > OH > NEt₂ > H
8.4 8.5 11.0 14.3 17.2 19.0

This order is irrespective of whether the nematogen is *p*-azoxyanisole or *p*-acetoxybenzylidene-*p*-phenetidine, the latter having been studied by Dave and Vasanth²¹ with other non-mesogens. Substituents with similar size have similar effects (Me, Cl). From the study of mixtures involving similar non-mesogenic compounds, differing in the central group, they deduced that the effect of the central group is either negligible or small. Dave and Dewar¹⁹ showed that birefringent two-component liquids are composed of single liquid crystalline phase. Hence, reproducible molecular weights could not be obtained using the method of depression of N-L point.

Dave *et al.*²² also studied binary systems of smectogens and poly mesogens. No order for the tendency of the terminal polar groups present in the non-mesogenic components to promote mixed smectic mesomorphism can be deduced

as the transition lines are almost all curved.

Acknowledgement

The author thanks Professor M. N. Patel, Head, Chemistry Department, Sardar Patel University, Vallabh Vidyanagar, for providing all facilities to deliver this lecture at his institute.

References

1. F. REINITZER, *Monatsh, Chem.*, 1888, 9, 421.
2. O. LEHMANN, *Z. Krystallogr.*, 1890, 18, 464.
3. G. FRIEDEL, *Ann. Phys.*, 1922, 18, 273.
4. "Liquid Crystals and Plastic Crystals," eds. G. W. GRAY and P. A. WINSOR, Vol. 1, Ellis Horwood, Chichester, 1974, p. x.
5. E. BOSE, *Phys. Z.*, 1909, 10, 32, 230.
6. C. WEYGAND, *Z. Phys. Chem. (B)*, 1942, 53, 75.
7. A SAUPE in "Liquid Crystals and Plastic Crystals", eds. G. W. GRAY and P. A. WINSOR, Ellis Horwood, Chichester, 1974, Vol. 1, p. 19.
8. H. SACKMANN and D. DEMUS, *Mol. Cryst.*, 1966, 2, 81.
9. H. ZOCHER, *Phys. Z.*, 1927, 28, 790.
10. J. W. MCBAIN in "Colloid Chemistry", ed. J. ALEXANDER, The Chemical Catalogue Co., New York, 1926, Vol. 1, p. 138.
11. G. W. GRAY in "Liquid Crystals", eds. G. H. BROWN, C. J. DIENES and M. M. LABES, Gordon and Breach, New York, 1967 p. 129.
12. J. S. DAVE and R. A. VORA, *Indian J Chem.*, 1973, 11, 19.
13. G. W. GRAY and B. JONES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 4179.
14. J. S. DAVE, G. KURIAN, A. P. PRAJAPATI and R. A. VORA, *Mol. Cryst. Liq. Cryst.*, 1971, 14, 307.
15. G. W. GRAY, "Molecular Structure and Properties of Liquid Crystals," Academic, New York, 1962, p. 163.
16. N. V. MADHUSUDAN, B. K. SADASHIV and K. P. L. MOODITHAYA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1979, 48, 613.
17. S. CHANDRASHEKHAR, B. K. SADASHIV and K. A. SURESH, *Pramana*, 1977, 9, 471.
18. Ref. 4, p. 48.
19. J. S. DAVE and M. J. S. DEWAR, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 4617; 1955, 4305.
20. J. S. DAVE and J. M. LOHAR, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1967, 1473; *Indian J. Chem.*, 1966, 4, 386.
21. J. S. DAVE and K. L. VASANTH, *Mol. Cryst.*, 1966, 2, 125; *Pramana, Suppl. No. 1*, 1975, 415.
22. J. S. DAVE, P. R. PATEL and K. L. VASANTH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1966, 4, 505; *Mol. Cryst. Liq. Cryst.*, 1969, 8, 93.